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Research Article

**THE RISING TREND OF SMOKING AMONG FEMALE
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³ Wmo At Thq 90s/B Sargodha.**Abstract:**

OBJECTIVE: The objective of the study is to find out the prevalence and different types of smoking among female medical students of different universities of Lahore and Multan.

STUDY DESIGN: It is a cross sectional type of study.

PLACE AND DURATION: The study was done from July 2017 to June 2018.

378 Female students from different universities were enrolled in the study, their identity was kept secret.

METHODOLOGY: The sample consisted of 378 females students selected on the basis of random consecutive sampling. A pre-formed questionnaire was made and given to them according to the study protocol.

RESULTS: The prevalence of smoking among females students was found to 16.8%. The mean age of smokers was 20.31±3.45 years. The sheesha, as a source of smoke was found to be popular among females medical students. Majority of the students were doing their graduation (business administration-23.1%, fashion designing 25.4%). It was noted that majority of the students become addicted to smoking in their teen ages 14-19 years.

CONCLUSION: Smoking is a rapidly increasing stigma of the society these days, with females are no exception. It is the need of the hour to take serious measure about this evil, so that further stigmatization may be prevented among students and other society members.

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INTRODUCTION:

The mortality rate due to smoking is quite higher than the mortality rates of accidents, suicides, alcohol consumption, injuries and murders. The number of deaths due to cancers as a consequence of smoking is on a rapid rise, 90% of deaths with lung cancers and 80% women with lung cancer are smokers. The other forms of tobacco in non smoke forms like chewing, beera, snuff etc are causing other forms of cancers. [1].

Due to globalization and behavioral changes, the trend of smoking among the females is rising and it has also been noted that the addiction in females is more intense and it is very difficult for them to give up this habit. World Health Organization emphasizes on the marketing of smoking and its impact especially in females in "Gender and tobacco" in 2011. The theme was to highlight the rising use of tobacco in females [2].

In Women, breast cancer is the most common type of cancer but the number of deaths due to smoking related cancers is now more than the number of deaths due to breast carcinoma. And frequency of death is way higher in patients aged more than 55 years with lung cancer. Moreover, a number of studies have highlighted the relationship of smoking and outcome of pregnancy. Smoking or use of other forms of tobacco can cause hazard to the health of mother as well as to that of embryo. Even the passive smoking has unabated risks to pregnant ladies. The hazards of smoking may range from congenital malformations to miscarriages and even deaths of gravida and the child [3].

Pregnant smokers are at a very high risk to produce underweight, premature and malformed babies and they more often suffer from abortions and miscarriages.

And the children may suffer from cognitive disability, difficulty in learning and develop mental problems in pregnant ladies who smoke. The water pipe and sheesha have been considered as safer but studies and experiments yielded opposite results, the amount of tar that is produced by water pipe is higher than the cigarettes. Water pipe smoking is considered safer than cigarettes but experiments have yielded opposite results [4]. The Sheesha smoking had been preferred by females in past few years and it was easily available in cafes, restaurants, sheesha bars and hotels. However, the respectively.

percentage of nicotine in sheesha is (2% – 4%) while in cigarettes (1% – 3%) [9, 10]. Now a days Sheesha smoking is becoming popular and usually parents allow their children to smoke sheesha due to lack of knowledge and proper information about its hazards. The objective of our study was to explore the prevalence of smoking in female students of Lahore and Multan universities.

METHODOLOGY:

It is a cross sectional type of study done from July 2016 to June 2017 for 12 months. The female students from five universities were enrolled in our study.

Two staged sampling was done, in first stage universities were selected in the second stage, females were enrolled by consecutive random sampling.

378 females from different institutions and different fields were enrolled in our study. The preformed questionnaires were given to them to collect the required information.

The data was recorded and analyzed by the help of spss version 21.0.

The cases were filtered through inclusion criteria. The unwilling subjects were dropped out of the study. The students were informed regarding the purpose of study and informed consent was taken for the conduction of this study. A preformed questionnaire was filled in by each student regarding the general basic details about his life and smoking history. The data and the identities were kept secret as per protocol of our study.

RESULTS:

The sample of our study consisted of 378 females with the mean age of 20.31 ± 3.45 years. The age of the subjects ranged between (15 – 29) years. Most of the females cases were not married, a few were married and very few were divorced. Almost 16.8 % of the subjects were addict to smoking. Only 2.7% of the subjects claimed that they have quit smoking.

Smoking included various types of tobacco usage, inhaled by different means (pipe, sheesha etc). The prevalence of smoking were the highest in students of Arts followed by students of business administration i.e 25.4% and 23.1%.

The bachelor’s level students from Fashion Designing and Business Administration departments were actively involved in smoking (24.2% and 22.6% respectively). The overall picture of smoking incidences in all the classes is summarized in charts

DISCUSSION:

The results of our study indicate an overall occurrence of 17.6% female students who smoke in five universities of Lahore and Multan. The trend of smoking among females, especially students, is rising in Pakistan and is a serious public health hazard.

Among various types of smoking, Sheesha is the most popular among female students and is unfortunately somewhat acceptable socially. A number of international and national studies have been done on this topic [5].

A study conducted in Mongolia and China in 2011 reported the percentage of female smoker as 1.7% that is much lower than the findings of our study. A national level study was conducted in Armed Forces Hospital Rawalpindi in 2006 reported that no woman health professional was involved in smoking except 3 nurses.

Yet another study done in Jordan on female students reported that 10.7% of the students were used to smoke. Another study reveals that six percent female college students in Riyadh were addicts to smoking [6].

Another study was performed in Saudi Arabia in 2007 to assess the prevalence of smoking. The results of it showed that a considerably large number Saudi female students were involved in use of tobacco; current smokers (11%), Sheesha & Pipe Smokers (8.7%), Cigarette smokers (5%). [7].

The results of our study about sheesha smoking were confirmed by another study done in female students of universities of Karachi, which reported that 16.8 % female students were addicted to sheesha smoking [8].

A number of national and international studies have been conducted and it has been confirmed that female teenager students are using tobacco more than any other age group. A study shows that, in Saudi Arabia the students who start to smoke have ages below 17 years. These results are in line with the results of other study that female students who smoke have started it during their teenage [9]. The results of our study were strengthened by a study done in Sind reporting that 44% female smokers aged 18-24 years. The results of our study also report that the upper teenage is the most prone to develop addiction to smoking. [10].

The rising trend of smoking in all across the world is stigmatizing the lives. The Muslim countries' women have not been previously seen with such addictions in such a high numbers. The rapid changes in globalization fashion industry and values strongly impacted the life styles of the females. Most of the females start smoking in the age (15 – 19) years, so, it is the need of the hour to make strict policies which could particularly target this age group [11]. Underage use of tobacco and sale should be banned and punished. The students should be prevented from using tobacco in the institutions and hostels etc. General awareness about the hazardous effects of tobacco smoking including betel nuts,

sheesha etc should be given to the people.

CONCLUSION:

The trend of smoking in the students is on a rise with the females no exception. It is urgently needed to formulate such policies which must have potential to control and discourage all types of smoking in general public and particularly among students.

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